

UNSYMMETRICAL BUCKLING OF LATERALLY LOADED REINFORCED

PLASTICS SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

The onset of unsymmetrical deflexions in laterally loaded curved shells, and the effects of unsymmetrical behaviour on the load displacement paths of such shells are examined in this paper. An analysis of a simple model structure; a curved bar with central spring, is made to illustrate the phenomenon and to indicate the main factors influencing the unsymmetrical behaviour. A further analysis of a more complex problem i.e. the behaviour of shallow orthotropic shells of rectangular planform under lateral point and pressure loading is outlined. The results of this analysis are compared with those of an experimental examination of the behaviour of curved glass reinforced plastics (GRP) plates, and good agreement is obtained.

1. INTRODUCTION

The behaviour of laterally loaded shallow shells and curved plates has been examined by a number of writers in the past, and the phenomenon of snap-through buckling is well understood. While many authors have investigated only the symmetrical behaviour of the plates and shells (1) (2) (3) some examinations of the effects of unsymmetrical deflexions have been published, particularly in the case of shallow spherical shells (4) (5).

In general the snap through effect has received the greatest attention from previous investigators. This effect occurs if the applied load reaches a maximum value at a certain deflexion magnitude and reduces with further increase in deflexion until the shell is inverted, whereupon the load increases once more. In such a case the maximum load is termed the buckling load and the loading path thereafter is unstable until the shell inverts. The effects of unsymmetrical deflexions are to reduce the buckling, and also to reduce the negative slope of the load-deflexion curve after buckling. However it can also happen that the onset of unsymmetrical behaviour can produce a completely stable load deflexion path in a situation where the symmetrical loading path is inherently unstable.

Such an effect was noted during a recent investigation into the behaviour of shallow orthotropic curved shells of rectangular planform (6). In this investigation it was found that for shells with length to width ratio

of about 1.50 or greater unsymmetrical deflexions occurred experimentally and no snap through occurred. The theoretical analysis however, based on an approximate solution of the Von Karman type large deflexion equations, and considering only symmetrical deflexions, predicted a substantial snap through effect. Thus it became obvious that the unsymmetrical deflexions had a great deal of influence on the shell behaviour. It was also noted that for square or nearly square planform shells the theoretical predictions based on symmetrical analysis were very accurate. As the aspect ratio increased the unsymmetrical effects became greater and the correlation between the theoretical and experimental results depreciated radically. For this reason the investigation described here was undertaken to examine the effects of unsymmetrical deflexions.

To obtain some indication of the various factors influencing the onset of unsymmetrical behaviour an approximate analysis of a simplified structure was first attempted.

2. SIMPLE ILLUSTRATIVE PROBLEM

The system analysed in this case is the sinusoidally correct beam and spring arrangement shown in Figure 1. The behaviour of a curved beam was examined by Fung and Kaplan (7) and summarised by Rushton.

Figure 1
Curved Beam

Figure 2
Load/Deflection Curve

For such a beam unsymmetrical deflexions only arise when snap-through is present and the unsymmetrical load displacement path is always negative as shown in Figure 2. The addition of a central spring is made by the writers to investigate the possibility of obtaining positive slope unsymmetrical paths. The behaviour of the system can be analysed approximately using an energy approach which gives simple expressions governing the behaviour, as follows.

The deflexions of the beam are assumed to have a symmetrical and an anti-symmetrical component.

$$\omega = \delta \sin \frac{\pi x}{l} + C \sin \frac{2\pi x}{l} \quad (1)$$

The bending energy stored in the beam and the strain energy of the spring can be evaluated from

$$U_B = \frac{EI}{2} \int_0^l \left(\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} K \delta^2 \quad (2)$$

Substituting from (1) and integrating gives

$$U_B = \frac{EI \pi^4}{4l^3} [\delta^2 + 16c^2] + \frac{1}{2} K \delta^2 = \frac{EI \pi^4}{4l^3} \left[\delta^2 \left(1 + \frac{2l^3 K}{\pi^4 EI} \right) + 16c^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

In this equation the strain energy in the spring is associated only with the symmetric deflexion and has been included in the bending energy corresponding to the symmetrical mode. The quantity $\left(1 + \frac{2l^3 K}{\pi^4 EI} \right)$ can be

denoted R for convenience and by varying R the relative bending energies per unit deflexion of the symmetrical and anti-symmetrical modes can be adjusted. This gives a simulation of the effect obtained in rectangular planform shells where the relative bending energies of each mode are dependent on the aspect ratio.

The membrane, or middle surface, strain in the beam can be obtained from a consideration of the change in middle-surface length of the beam during bending. The initial length is greater than l by an amount

$$u_0 = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left[\frac{d}{dx} \left(h \sin \frac{\pi x}{l} \right) \right]^2 dx \quad (4)$$

After bending the total change in length is

$$u = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left[\frac{d}{dx} \left((h - \delta) \sin \frac{\pi x}{l} + c \sin \frac{2\pi x}{l} \right) \right]^2 dx \quad (5)$$

The middle surface strain is then

$$\epsilon = \frac{u_0 - u}{l} \quad (6)$$

Performing the differentiations and integrations gives

$$\epsilon = \frac{\pi^2}{4l^2} [2h\delta - \delta^2 - 4c^2] \quad (7)$$

The strain energy associated with middle surface strains can be evaluated using the expression $U_M = \int \frac{E\epsilon^2}{2} dV$, thus obtaining

$$U_M = \frac{E\pi^4}{32l^3} \cdot bd [2h\delta - \delta^2 - 4c^2]^2 \quad (8)$$

The potential energy lost by the load, U_L , is dependent only on the symmetrical deflexions, since the anti-symmetrical term gives zero displacement at the load point.

$$\text{Thus } U_L = -P\delta \quad (9)$$

The total potential of the system is found from the sum of U_S , U_M and U_L , giving

$$U_T = \frac{E\pi^4}{l^3} \left\{ \left[\frac{I}{4} [R\delta^2 + 16c^2] + \frac{bd}{32} [2h\delta - \delta^2 - 4c^2]^2 \right] - P\delta \right\} \quad (10)$$

For convenience this can be rearranged, noting that $I = bd^3/12$, to give

$$U_T = \frac{EI\pi^4 R h^2}{2l^3} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^2 + \frac{16}{R} \left(\frac{c}{h}\right)^2 \right] + \frac{3}{4R} \left(\frac{h}{d}\right)^2 \left[2\left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right) - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^2 - 4\left(\frac{c}{h}\right)^2 \right]^2 \right\} - P\delta \quad (11)$$

The Principle of Minimum Potential Energy requires that $\frac{\partial U_T}{\partial C} = 0$ and

$$\frac{\partial U_T}{\partial \delta} = 0. \text{ Applying the former condition gives} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{EI\pi^4 R h}{2l^3} \left\{ \frac{16}{R} \left(\frac{c}{h}\right) - \frac{12}{R} \left(\frac{c}{h}\right) \left(\frac{h}{d}\right)^2 \left[2\left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right) - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^2 - 4\left(\frac{c}{h}\right)^2 \right] \right\} = 0$$

This equation is satisfied at all times if $C = 0$, showing that a symmetrical load deflexion path is possible throughout the range of behaviour. If $C \neq 0$ then equation (12) is satisfied if

$$\left(\frac{c}{h}\right) = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2\left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right) - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^2 - \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{d}{h}\right)^2} \quad (13)$$

Thus the case of $C \neq 0$, i.e. the onset of unsymmetric behaviour is dependent only on the values of $\frac{\delta}{h}$ and $\frac{d}{h}$, and is not influenced by the spring stiffness via R .

$$\text{Setting } \frac{\partial U_T}{\partial \delta} = 0 \text{ gives} \quad (14)$$

$$P = \frac{EI\pi^4 R h}{2l^3} \left[\left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right) + \frac{3}{R} \left(\frac{h}{d}\right)^2 \left(1 - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)\right) \left[2\left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right) - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^2 - 4\left(\frac{c}{h}\right)^2 \right] \right]$$

It can easily be shown that the quantity $\frac{EI\pi^4 R}{2l^3}$ is the stiffness of the beam spring combination obtained by linear simple bending theory, S_L . For example

with $R = 1$ (no spring) then $S_L = \frac{\pi^4 EI}{2 l^3} = 48.7 \frac{EI}{l^3}$. (Accurate linear analysis gives $S_L = 48 \frac{EI}{l^3}$).

Equation (14) can therefore be written

$$\frac{P}{h S_L} = \frac{\delta}{h} + \frac{3}{R} \left(\frac{h}{a}\right)^2 \left(1 - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)\right) \left(2 - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right) - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^2 - 4 \left(\frac{c}{h}\right)^2\right) \quad (15)$$

If $C = 0$ the symmetric loading path is obtained as

$$\frac{P}{h S_L} = \frac{\delta}{h} + \frac{3}{R} \left(\frac{h}{a}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{\delta}{h} \left(1 - \frac{\delta}{h}\right) \left(2 - \frac{\delta}{h}\right) \quad (16)$$

The unsymmetrical loading path is obtained by substituting for C from equation (13), giving

$$\frac{P}{h S_L} = \frac{\delta}{h} + \frac{4}{R} \left(1 - \frac{\delta}{h}\right) \quad (17)$$

Therefore the unsymmetrical path gives a straight line variation of deflexion with load. From equation (13) it can be seen that a value of C other than zero only exists if $\frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{d}{h}\right)$ is less than $2 \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right) - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^2$. Therefore at small values of δ , unsymmetrical behaviour does not occur. Also, since the maximum value of $2 \frac{\delta}{h} - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^2$ is 1 then no unsymmetrical behaviour will occur if $\left(\frac{d}{h}\right)^2 < \frac{4}{3}$. As the rise, h , of the beam increases beyond $\frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} d$ the onset of unsymmetrical behaviour occurs at a decreasing value of $\frac{\delta}{h}$ and the effects of unsymmetric behaviour become increasingly pronounced.

Figure 3 illustrates this behaviour. The factor R is set equal to 1 for this figure so that the curves shown are for the beam only with zero spring stiffness. As can be seen for values of $\frac{h}{a}$ less than $\frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}$ the paths

Figure 3
Effect of Beam Curvature

are symmetrical. For higher values of $\frac{h}{d}$ the symmetrical path intersects the unsymmetrical path and bifurcation from the symmetrical to the unsymmetrical occurs. Where the paths intersect the unsymmetrical path always constitutes a path of lesser potential energy than the symmetrical path, and if unsymmetrical behaviour is possible it will always occur.

It is worthy of note that for a beam of given section and length, the slope of the unsymmetrical path is independent of the initial height, h .

For the symmetrical paths the turning values of the load can be obtained by differentiating P with respect to δ in equation (16) to get

$$\frac{P_{\max}}{hS_L} , \frac{P_{\min}}{hS_L} = 1 \pm \frac{6}{R} \left(\frac{h}{d}\right)^2 \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{R}{9} \left(\frac{h}{d}\right)^2\right)^3} \quad (18)$$

This shows that for $R > 3 \left(\frac{h}{d}\right)^2$ the load-deflexion path has no turning values. It is interesting to note that at $h = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} d$, i.e. the minimum rise for unsymmetrical behaviour, the lower turning value of P is zero.

The value of load at which bifurcation occurs can be obtained by finding the value of δ to give real roots of equation (14) and substituting into equation (17). This gives

$$\frac{P_B}{hS_L} = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{4}{R}\right) \sqrt{1 - \frac{4}{3} R \left(\frac{d}{h}\right)^2} \quad (19)$$

Figure 4 shows the effect of varying R on the load-deflexion paths.

Figure 4
Effect of Varying 'R'

For $R = 1$, i.e. zero spring stiffness, the unsymmetrical path is unstable (negative slope) and snap-through buckling occurs. As the spring stiffness is increased the slope of the unsymmetrical path changes so that at $R = 4$ the slope is zero, i.e. the unsymmetrical path is neutral. For $R > 4$ the unsymmetrical path is stable and no snap through is obtained.

The general effect of increasing R is to increase the bending energy associated with the symmetrical mode deflexions relative to that associated with anti-symmetrical deflexions.

3. EFFECTS OF ANTI-SYMMETRICAL IMPERFECTIONS

The effects of anti-symmetrical imperfections can be examined by considering that the initial shape of the beam has the form $w_0 = h \sin \frac{\pi C}{C} + \Delta \sin \frac{\ell \pi C}{\ell}$. The quantity Δ may be referred to as the anti-symmetrical imperfection magnitude. If this initial form is examined and the same deflexion functions are used, the presence of the anti-symmetrical term makes it impossible to obtain simple closed form expressions for the load-deflexion path as were obtained before. Instead, by performing the analysis as before two equations are obtained as follows

$$4 \left(\frac{c}{h}\right)^3 - 12 \left(\frac{c}{h}\right)^2 \frac{\Delta}{h} + \left(8 \left(\frac{\Delta}{h}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^2 - 2 \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right) + \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{d}{h}\right)^2\right) \left(\frac{c}{h}\right) + 2 \frac{\delta}{h} \frac{\Delta}{h} \left(2 - \frac{\delta}{h}\right) = 0 \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{P}{h S_L} = \frac{\delta}{h} + \frac{3}{R} \left(\frac{h}{d}\right)^2 \left(1 - \frac{\delta}{h}\right) \left(2 \frac{\delta}{h} - \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^2\right) + 4 \left(\frac{2 \Delta c}{h^2} - \left(\frac{c}{h}\right)^2\right) \quad (21)$$

To obtain load deflexion paths for a specified system then the value of C for a given δ can be obtained from equation (20) and substituted into (21) to obtain P .

The effects of anti-symmetrical imperfections are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5.

Effects of Anti-Symmetrical Imperfections

For the spring/beam combinations examined here $R = 3$ and the unsymmetrical path for the system without imperfections is unstable. As can be seen from this figure the introduction of anti-symmetrical imperfections can make the equilibrium path completely stable.

In general therefore, the simple analysis shows that if there is a great difference between the bending energies associated with anti-symmetrical and symmetrical mode deflexions, then the unsymmetrical path will be unstable. If the bending energies of the two modes are not so widely different then the unsymmetrical path tends to become stable.

If anti-symmetrical imperfections are present then a system which would, if perfect, have an unstable unsymmetrical path can be induced to follow a perfectly stable path due to the imperfections.

4. COMMENT ON THE ACCURACY OF THE ANALYSIS

The aim of this rather crude analysis was simply to examine the causes and effects of unsymmetrical behaviour without undue note being taken of the accuracy of the analysis. However, on comparing results for $R = 1$, i.e. zero spring stiffness with those quoted by Rushton (8) from Fung and Kaplan's analysis (7) it would appear that the agreement is surprisingly good. Rushton quoted buckling loads for central loading, uniform pressure loading, and sinusoidally varying loading. For these symmetrical loading cases the analysis presented here can be used with only the potential energy term, $-P\delta$, being altered. For a uniform loading $-P\delta$ can be replaced by $-\int_0^l p \cdot \delta \sin \frac{\pi x}{l} dx$, i.e. $-\frac{2pl\delta}{\pi}$ and for sinusoidal loading $p_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{l}$ then $-P\delta$ can be replaced by $-\int_0^l p_0 \delta \sin^2 \frac{\pi x}{l} dx$, i.e. $-p_0 l \delta$. Values obtained using this analysis are compared with those quoted by Rushton in Table 1.

Table 1

Loading	Ref (8)			Authors		symmetrical or unsymmetrical
	$\frac{h}{d}$	$\frac{P_{\max} l^3}{EI d}$	$\frac{P_{\min} l^3}{EI d}$	$\frac{P_{\max} l^3}{EI d}$	$\frac{P_{\min} l^3}{EI d}$	
$p_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{l}$	1	158.6	36.2	159.8	36.5	s
$p_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{l}$	2	672	<0	667.2	<0	u
p per unit length	2	527.7	-	524		u
P at centre	2	325.9		333.6		u

In the previous table the quantity P_{\max} and P_{\min} refers to the total lateral load regardless of how it is applied. From the table it can be seen that the results of the present analysis are very close to those quoted by Rushton. Unfortunately the authors have not as yet been able to obtain ref. (7) and do not have details of Fung and Kaplan's analysis. However the results are quoted by Rushton as 'exact'.

5. BEHAVIOUR OF ORTHOTROPIC CURVED PANELS

A similar method of approach was used to theoretically and experimentally examine the problem of orthotropic curved panels under lateral loading. For this case the labour involved was, of necessity, somewhat more protracted

than for the simple case illustrated. The panels had constant curvature in both principal directions and were laminated using Uni-directional GRP.

Figure 6.
GRP Panels

The boundary conditions considered were simply supported edges, free from normal and shear stress. The method of approach to this problem has been detailed in ref. (6) for the symmetrical deflexion case. This involves the postulation of a series form for the lateral deflexions w , and evaluation of the corresponding stress system by solving the compatibility equation. If imperfections, w_0 , are present the compatibility equation can be written

$$\frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^4} + \alpha \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \beta \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial y^4} = E_y \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x \partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right\} \quad (22)$$

For the boundary conditions under examination an exact solution to equation (22) is not possible and resort was made to an approximate solution using Galerkin's method together with an assumed series form for the stress function F .

The final solution is obtained by evaluating the total potential energy of the system in terms of F , w and U the potential lost by the loading using the following expression

$$U_T = U_S + U_B + U_p \quad (23)$$

where

$$U_S = \frac{h}{2} \iint \left[\frac{1}{E_x} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 - 2 \nu_x \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} \right) + \frac{1}{G} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{E_y} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 \right] dx dy$$

$$U_B = \frac{1}{2} \iint \left[D_1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + 2 D_3 \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 + D_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 \right] dx dy$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_p &= - \iint w \cdot p \cdot dx dy \\
 &= - P \sum_m \sum_n w_{mn} (-1)^{\frac{m+n}{2}+1} \dots \text{for point load at centre.} \\
 &= -4 p \frac{ab}{\pi^2} \sum_m \sum_n \frac{1}{mn} \cdot w_{mn} \dots \text{for uniform pressure loading.}
 \end{aligned}$$

It was found that for the symmetrical analysis the solution obtained using only one term in the deflexion and stress function series gave load-deflexion paths close to those obtained using many more terms these series, and indeed close to experimental paths for square or nearly square planform panels which had no tendency to deflect unsymmetrically. Details of the experimental investigation are contained in (9).

In view of this, and in the light of the findings of the examination of the simple bar and spring problem, it was decided that the following approximate expressions be used to describe the deflexions, anti-symmetric imperfections and stress function respectively:-

$$\begin{aligned}
 w &= w_{11} \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} + w_{12} \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{2\pi y}{b} \\
 w_0 &= \Delta \sin \frac{2\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \\
 F &= F_1 \sin^2 \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin^2 \frac{\pi y}{b} + F_2 \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{2\pi x}{a} \sin^2 \frac{\pi y}{b}
 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

The form for w incorporates a symmetrical function and a function which is anti-symmetrical in the x direction. The form for w_0 describes an imperfection anti-symmetrical in the x direction, and the form for F includes a symmetrical component and a component which is anti-symmetrical in the x direction. By substitution of equations (24) into (22), evaluating the total potential energy from (23) and applying the principal of Minimum Potential Energy, two equations analogous to equations (20) and (21) were set up. These equations, which are not presented here because of their length, provided the load and deflexion paths for panels with given material properties and dimensions.

The properties of the GRP panels tested were as follows:-

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_x &= 31.78 \text{ GN/m}^2 & \nu_x &= 0.333 \\
 E_y &= 10.25 \text{ GN/m}^2 & G_{xy} &= 2.142 \text{ GN/m}^2
 \end{aligned}$$

In all cases examined it was found that if an imperfection of maximum amplitude equal to 1.5 times the panel thickness was used then the resulting theoretical paths agreed well with the experimental paths. Examples are

shown in Figures 7 and 8 for point loaded panels, and in Figures 9 and 10 for panels with uniformly distributed loading.

As the graphs show, in all cases the symmetrical path is highly unstable whereas the experimental path is completely stable. This stable experimental path is followed with good agreement by the theoretical paths with imperfections of 1.5 times the thickness. It is of note here that the unsymmetrical paths for panels without imperfections are unstable.

In the case of panels the variations in membrane stresses within the panels caused the unsymmetrical paths for perfect curved panels to be non-

Figure 7
Orthotropic Shell Under Central Point Loading
Aspect Ratio $\lambda = 1.50$

Figure 8
Orthotropic Shell Under Central Point Loading
Aspect Ratio $\lambda = 1.75$

Figure 9
Orthotropic Shell Under Uniform Pressure Loading
Aspect Ratio $\lambda = 1.5$

Figure 10
Orthotropic Shell Under Uniform Pressure Loading
Aspect Ratio $\lambda = 1.75$

linear (rather than linear as for the illustrative beam problem), and the effects of imperfections are to linearise the unsymmetrical paths.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The mechanism of unsymmetrical behaviour in curved bars and shells has been illustrated with respect to a simple model, and it has been demonstrated that both stable and unstable unsymmetrical paths are possible. The presence of unsymmetrical imperfections have been found in all cases to increase the slope of the unsymmetrical path at all points, thus reducing

the possibility of snap-through.

Application of the methods used to examine the problem of GRP curved panels has been shown to produce reasonable agreement with experimental results.

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APPENDIX I

Comparison between theoretical and experimental studies.